

Step-By-Step Application of Shifted Legendre Polynomials on Numerical Assessment of Non-Linear Bratu Differential Equations

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Abstract

The approximate solution of Bratu differential equations was obtained using the modified variational iteration algorithm with shifted Legendre polynomials. The suggested modification is created by constructing shifted Legendre polynomials for the provided problem and using them as the basis functions for the approximation. To show that the recommended approach is efficient, dependable, and reliable, two test problems were also provided. The maple 18 program was used to perform the calculations.

Keyword: Differential equations, variational iteration technique, shifted Legendre polynomials, bratu equations, approximate solution.

Introduction

Application of numerical solution in solving various forms of real-life problems involving all kinds of equations, some of which may not have analytical solution is one of the interests of researchers in computational mathematics. Otaide et al. (2023) and Otaide et al. (2024) for examples, applied shifted Vieta Lucas polynomials differently in their work. Fadugba et al. (2023) considered applicability and analysis of trigonometric - exponential single-step method for the numerical solution of HIV-1 model while Otaide & Oluwayemi (2024) also considered linear Volterra integro differential equations using variational iteration algorithm with collocation. In this work however, the authors are interested in a step-by-step application of shifted Legendre polynomials on numerical assessment of non-linear Bratu differential equations. The initial thermal combustion theory, which was developed by the simplification of the solid fuel ignition model, is what is known as a one-dimensional Bratu-type problem and is what gives Eqn (1) its significance. To this end, numerous studies on Bratu-type differential equations have been conducted. Salema & Thanoona (2022) used the perturbation method to solve the problem of the Bratu type. Zarebnia & Hoshyar (2014) employed spline technique for the solution of Bratu's type problem. Wazwaz (2016) used method of successive differentiation for solving Bratu's type equations. Saravi et al. (2013) used the He's variational Iteration Method for the solution of Bratu's equation. For the numerical solution of second order initial value problems of Bratu-type equations, Fenta & Derese (2019) used the sixth order Runge-Kutta seven stages technique. Bratu-type problems were addressed by Ezekiel (2013) using the New Improved Variational Homotopy Perturbation Technique. The Bratu's problem was approximated analytically by Hassan & Semaary (2013) using the optimal homotopy analysis technique. When solving the Bratu problem numerically, Aregbesola (2003) employed the weighted residual technique. For the handling of equations of the Bratu's type, Wazwaz (2005) employed Adomians' decomposition technique. For the resolution of Bratu's problem, Changqing & Jianhua (2013) used the Chebyshev wavelets method. In this study, the numerical solution of Bratu's differential equation (1) with provided initial conditions (2) is obtained using variational iteration algorithm using shifted Legendre polynomials.

$$\frac{d^2\varphi}{d\tau^2} + \gamma e^{\alpha\varphi} = 0; \quad 0 < \tau < 1; \quad \gamma, \alpha \in \mathfrak{R} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{with initial conditions } \varphi(\tau) = \varphi'(\tau) = 0; \quad \tau = 0. \quad (2)$$

The findings thus far are positive and trustworthy, and the suggested strategy operates effectively.

The Essential Concept of the Variational Iteration Algorithm

We consider the following general differential problem to demonstrate the technique's fundamental idea.

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$$L\varphi + N_l\varphi - g(\tau) = 0, \quad (3)$$

The inhomogeneous term is $g(\tau)$, L and N_l are linear and nonlinear operators, respectively.

We can create a correction functional as follows using the variational iteration analysis.

$$\varphi_{i+1} = \varphi(\tau) + \int_0^\tau \lambda(L\varphi_i + N_l\tilde{\varphi}_i - g)dt \quad (4)$$

In this case, the variational iteration technique can be used to most effectively identify the Lagrange multiplier $\lambda(t)$. The n th approximation is indicated by the subscript n , and the limited variation $\tilde{\varphi}_i$ is regarded as such. i.e $\tilde{\varphi}_i=0$. Thus, the Lagrange multiplier is precisely identified and the problems can be solved in a single iteration phase. The successive approximation of the solution will be easily obtained using the langrange multiplier and our φ_0 in this technique, because we need to find the langrange multiplier $\lambda(t)$ optimally.

The solution is given by

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \varphi_i = \varphi$$

The Lagrange multiplier, which has the following definitions, is also crucial in determining how to solve the problem.

$$(-1)^n \frac{1}{(n-1)!} (t - \tau)^{n-1}$$

Legendre Polynomials

The Legendre polynomials is an orthogonal polynomial with weight function $w(x) = 1$ and defined as:

$$P_n(\tau) = \frac{1}{2^n n!} \frac{d^n}{d\tau^n} (\tau^2 - 1)^n : -1 < \tau < 1$$

In light of this, the first few Legendre equations are provided below:

$$P_0(\tau) = 1, P_1(\tau) = \tau, P_2(\tau) = \frac{3}{2}\tau^2 - \frac{1}{2}, \dots \quad (5)$$

4. Shifted Legendre Polynomials

The Shifted Legendre polynomials are defined as:

$$P_n^*(\tau) = \frac{1}{n!} \frac{d^n}{d\tau^n} (\tau^2 - \tau)^n : 0 < \tau < 1$$

In light of this, the first few Shifted Legendre polynomials are provided below:

$$P^*_0(\tau) = 1, P^*_{1}(\tau) = 2\tau - 1, P^*_{2}(\tau) = 6\tau^2 - 6\tau + 1, \dots \quad (6)$$

Modified Variational Iteration Algorithm Using Shifted Legendre Polynomials

We presume a rough solution of the form using (3) and (4).

$$\varphi_{i,N}(\tau) = \sum_{i=0}^N \xi_{i,N} P^*_{i,N}(\tau)$$

Where $\xi_{i,N}$ are unknown values, N is the degree of approximation, and $P^*_{i,N}(\tau)$ are Shifted Legendre polynomials.

As a result, we arrive at the iterative approach below.

$$\varphi_{i+1,N}(\tau) = \sum_{i=0}^N \xi_{i,N} P^*_{i,N}(\tau) + \int_0^\tau \lambda(L \sum_{i=0}^N \xi_{i,N} P^*_{i,N}(t) + N_l \sum_{i=0}^N \xi_{i,N-1} P^*_{i,N}(t))dt \quad (7)$$

Convergence of the Method

This section will provide the Banach's theorem regarding the convergence of the variational iteration algorithm employing Shifted Legendre polynomials. The technique transforms the provided differential equation into a series of recurrences of functions. The limit of this sequence is assumed to contain the solution to the specified differential equation.

Theorem 1.

Let \mathcal{M} be a Banach space and $\mathfrak{S}: \mathcal{M} \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$ a nonlinear mapping, and assume that

$$\|\mathfrak{S}[\varphi] - \mathfrak{S}[\bar{\varphi}]\| \leq \zeta \|\varphi - \bar{\varphi}\|, \forall \varphi, \bar{\varphi} \in \mathcal{M}: \zeta < 1. \quad (8)$$

Then \mathfrak{S} has a unique fixed point. Hence, the sequence

$$\varphi_{i+1} = \mathfrak{S}[\varphi_i] \quad (9)$$

with an arbitrary choice of $w_0 \in \mathcal{M}$ converges to the fixed point of \mathfrak{S} and we have that

$$\|\varphi_p - \varphi_1\| \leq \|\varphi_p - \varphi_{p-1}\| + \dots + \|\varphi_{q+1} - \varphi_q\|$$

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$$\begin{aligned} &= \|\mathfrak{H}(\varphi_{p-1}) - \mathfrak{H}(\varphi_{p-2})\| + \dots + \|\mathfrak{H}(\varphi_q) - \mathfrak{H}(\varphi_{q-1})\| \\ &\leq \zeta \|\varphi_{p-1} - \varphi_{p-2}\| + \dots + \zeta \|\varphi_q - \varphi_{q-1}\| \\ &\leq (\zeta^{p-2} + \zeta^{p-3} + \dots + \zeta^{q-1}) \|\varphi_1 - \varphi_0\| \leq \frac{\zeta^{q-1}}{1-\zeta} \|\varphi_1 - \varphi_0\|, \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

Where $\zeta < 1$, based on the assumption that $p > q \geq 1$. These yields $\|\varphi_p - \varphi_q\| \rightarrow 0$ as $p, q \rightarrow \infty$ and hence the sequence $\{\varphi_p: p = 1 \dots \infty\}$ is Cauchy. Since \mathcal{M} is a Banach space the sequence is convergent and converges to a fixed point. By theorem 1, for nonlinear mapping we have that

$$\mathfrak{H}[\varphi] = \varphi_{i,N}(\tau) + \int_0^\tau \lambda(t)(L\varphi_i(t) + N\overline{\varphi_i(t)} - g(t))dt \tag{11}$$

$$\mathfrak{H}[\varphi] = \sum_{i=0}^N \xi_{i,N} P^*_{i,N}(\tau) + \int_0^\tau \lambda(t)(L\varphi_i(t) + N\overline{\varphi_i(t)} - g(t))dt \tag{12}$$

and this is a sufficient condition for the convergence of the variational iteration method using Shifted Legendre polynomials, which is strictly a contraction on \mathfrak{H} . In the sequel, the sequence (9) converges to a fixed point of \mathfrak{H} which is also a solution of (3).

Theoretical Perspectives to the problem

This section of the paper should contain the relevant theoretical viewpoints that explain or clarify the problem under study.

Empirical Perspectives to the problem

Numerical Applications

In this section, two Bratu-type problems were solved using the suggested methodology. Numerical results show the reliability of the proposed scheme.

Test Problem 1. [1]

Consider the Bratu-type problem (1), by choosing $\gamma = -2$ and $\alpha = 1$ to obtain:

$$\frac{d^2\varphi}{d\tau^2} - 2e^\varphi = 0, \quad 0 < \tau < 1, \tag{13}$$

$$\varphi(0) = \varphi'(0) = 0 \tag{14}$$

The theoretical solution of the system (13), is given as:

$$\varphi(\tau) = \tau^2 + \frac{\tau^4}{6} + \frac{2\tau^6}{45} + \frac{17\tau^8}{1260} + \dots$$

For problems (13) and (14) with initial conditions, the correction functional is provided as

$$\varphi_{i+1} = \varphi(\tau) + \int_0^\tau \lambda(\varphi'' - 2e^\varphi)dt$$

Where, $\lambda = \frac{(-1)^2(t-\tau)^1}{1!}$ is the Lagrange multiplier.

Using the Shifted Legendre polynomials and the reconstructed variational iteration technique, we assume an approximation of the solution of the form

$$\varphi_{i,2}(\tau) = \sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P^*_{i,N}(\tau)$$

Thus, we obtain the iterative formula shown below:

$$\varphi_{i+1,N}(\tau) = \sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P^*_{i,N}(\tau) + \int_0^\tau \frac{(-1)^2(t-\tau)^1}{1!} \left(\frac{d^2}{dt^2} (\sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P^*_{i,N}(t)) - 2e^{\sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P^*_{i,N}(t)} \right) dt$$

$$\varphi_{i+1,N}(\tau) = \xi_{0,2} P^*_{0,2}(\tau) + \xi_{1,2} P^*_{1,2}(\tau) + \xi_{2,2} P^*_{2,2}(\tau) + \int_0^\tau \frac{(-1)^2(t-\tau)^1}{1!} \left(\frac{d^2}{dt^2} (\sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P^*_{i,N}(t)) - 2e^{\sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P^*_{i,N}(t)} \right) dt$$

Consequently, by utilizing (6), iterating, and applying the initial conditions (14), it is possible to calculate the values of the unknown constants as

$$\xi_{0,2} = 0, \quad \xi_{1,2} = 0, \quad \xi_{2,2} = 0,$$

The series solution is therefore provided as $\varphi(\tau) = \tau^2$

Table 1: A comparison between the theoretical and the approximate solution

τ	Theoretical solution	Approximate solution	Absolute error based on the suggested method
0.1	0.0100167112	0.0100000000	0.0000167112
0.2	0.0402695456	0.0400000000	0.0002695456
0.3	0.0913832852	0.0900000000	0.0013832852
0.4	0.1644575533	0.1600000000	0.0044575533
0.5	0.2611638145	0.2500000000	0.0111638145
0.6	0.3839002149	0.3600000000	0.0239002149
0.7	0.5360233017	0.4900000000	0.0460233017
0.8	0.7221811037	0.6400000000	0.0821811037
0.9	0.9487774909	0.8100000000	0.1387774909

Figure1: graphical comparison of approximate and theoretical solution for Test problem 1

TEST PROBLEM 2. [1]

Consider the Bratu-type problem (1), by choosing $\gamma = -1$ and $\alpha = 2$ to obtain:

$$\frac{d^2\varphi}{d\tau^2} - e^{2\varphi} = 0, \quad 0 < \tau < 1, \quad (15)$$

$$\varphi(0) = \varphi'(0) = 0 \quad (16)$$

The theoretical solution of the system (10), is given as:

$$\varphi(\tau) = \frac{\tau^2}{2} + \frac{\tau^4}{12} + \frac{\tau^6}{45} + \frac{17\tau^8}{2520} + \dots$$

For problems (15) and (16) with initial conditions, the correction functional is provided as

$$\varphi_{i+1} = \varphi_i(\tau) + \int_0^\tau \lambda(\varphi'' - e^{2\varphi})dt$$

Where, $\lambda = \frac{(-1)^2(t-\tau)^1}{1}$ is the Lagrange multiplier.

Using the Shifted Legendre polynomials and the modified variational iteration technique, we assume an approximation of the solution of the form

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$$\varphi_{i,2}(\tau) = \sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P^*_{i,N}(\tau)$$

Thus, we obtain the iterative formula shown below:

$$\varphi_{i+1,N}(\tau) = \sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P^*_{i,N}(\tau) + \int_0^\tau \frac{(-1)^2(t-\tau)^1}{1!} \left(\frac{d^2}{dt^2} (\sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P^*_{i,N}(t)) - e^{2 \sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P^*_{i,N}(t)} \right) dt$$

$$\varphi_{i+1,N}(\tau) = \xi_{0,2} P^*_{0,2}(\tau) + \xi_{1,2} P^*_{1,2}(\tau) + \xi_{2,2} P^*_{2,2}(\tau) + \int_0^\tau \frac{(-1)^2(t-\tau)^1}{1!} \left(\frac{d^2}{dt^2} (\sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P^*_{i,N}(t)) - e^{2 \sum_{i=0}^2 \xi_{i,2} P^*_{i,N}(t)} \right) dt$$

Consequently, by utilizing (6), iterating, and applying the initial conditions (16), it is possible to calculate the values of the unknown constants as

$$\xi_{0,2} = 0, \quad \xi_{1,2} = 0, \quad \xi_{2,2} = 0,$$

The series solution is therefore provided as $\varphi(\tau) = \frac{1}{2} \tau^2$

Table 2: A comparison between the theoretical and the approximate solution

τ	Theoretical solution	Approximate solution	Absolute error based on the suggested method
0.1	0.0050083556	0.0050000000	0.0000083556
0.2	0.0201347728	0.0200000000	0.0001347728
0.3	0.0456916426	0.0450000000	0.0006916426
0.4	0.0822287766	0.0800000000	0.0022287766
0.5	0.1305819072	0.1250000000	0.0055819072
0.6	0.1919501074	0.1800000000	0.0119501074
0.7	0.2680116508	0.2450000000	0.0230116508
0.8	0.3610905518	0.3200000000	0.0410905518
0.9	0.4743887455	0.4050000000	0.0693887455

Figure 2: graphical comparison of approximate and theoretical solution for Test problem 2

Conclusion

This study has effectively produced numerical solutions for Bratu differential equations utilizing the reconstructed variational iteration analysis using shifted Legendre polynomials. Shifted Legendre polynomials combined with a variational iteration technique make up the solution's methodology. The method offers convergent series solutions, which show up in physical issues. From Tables 1 and 2, it is evident that the suggested strategy converges when compared to the theoretical solution. Beyond recall, the numerical results showed that the current approach is an effective mathematical tactic for handling the class of problems under study.

Competing Interests

The authors have declared that no competing interest exist

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References

- Aregbesola Y. (2003). Numerical solution of Bratu problem using the method of weighted residual. *Elect. J. South African Math. Soc.* 3(1) 1–7.
- Changqing Y. and Jianhua H. (2013). Chebyshev wavelets method for solving Bratu’s problem. *Bound. Value Prob.* 2013(1) 1–9.
- Ezekiel A. (2013). New Improved Variational Homotopy Perturbation Method for Bratu-Type Problems. *Amer. J. Comput. Math.* 3(2) 110–113.
- Fadugba S.E., Shaalini V.J., Oluwayemi M.O., Kekana M. C. (2023). Applicability and analysis of trigonometric - exponential single-step method for the numerical solution of HIV-1 model, *Communications in Mathematical Biology and Neuroscience*, 2023, 2023:46, 1-15, <https://doi.org/10.28919/cmbn/7923>.
- Fenta H.B. and Derese G.A. (2019). Numerical solution of second order initial value problems of Bratu-type equations using sixth order Runge-Kutta seven stages method. *Int. J. Comput. Sci. Appl. Math.* 5(1): 10-14.
- Hassan H.N. and Semary M. S. (2013). Analytic approximate solution for the Bratu’s problem by optimal homotopy analysis method. *Commun. Numerical Anal.* 1-14.
- Otaide I. J., Oluwayemi M. O. (2024). Numerical treatment of linear volterra integro differential equations using variational iteration algorithm with collocation, *Partial Differential Equations and Applied Mathematics* 1-8, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.padiff.2024.100693>.
- Otaide I. J., Oluwayemi M. O. and Odeh K. O. (2024). Application of Shifted Vieta-Lucas Polynomials for the Numerical Treatment of Volterra-Integro Differential Equations, *Proceedings of Journal of Nigerian Society of Physical Sciences (PJNSPS)*, 1(2024) 84, doi: I:10.61298/pnspsc.2024.1.84.
- Otaide I. J. Mark K. O. Modebei I. Oyedepo T., Oluwayemi M. O. (2023). Variational iteration algorithm for numerical solutions of sixth and seventh order boundary value problems using shifted Vieta Lucas polynomials, *Scientific African*, 22(2023), 1-10, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2023.e01924>.
- Salema S. A. , Thanooona T. Y. (2022). On solving Bratu’s type equation by perturbation Method. *Int. J. Nonlinear Anal. Appl.* 13(1): 2755-2763, <http://dx.doi.org/10.22075/ijnaa.2022.6000>.
- Zarebnia M. and Hoshyar M. (2014) . Solution of Bratu-type equation via spline method, *Acta Universitatis Apulensis*, 37, 61–72.
- Saravi M., Hermann and Kaiser D. (2013). Solution of Bratu’s Equation by He’s variational Iteration Method. *Amer. J. Comput. Appl. Math.* 3(1): 46–48.
- Wazwaz A.M. (2005). Adomians decomposition method for a reliable treatment of the Bratu-type equations. *Appl. Math. Comput.* 166, 652–663.
- Wazwaz A.M. (2016). The successive differentiation method for solving Bratu equation and Bratu-type equations, *Rom. J. Phys.* 61 774–783.